

Koszalin University of Technology

CoARA Action Plan 2025 - 2028

Under the Regulation of the Council of Ministers of June 8, 1968, the university was established as the Higher School of Engineering in Koszalin. It is located in the coastal belt surrounded by two large scientific and didactic districts. Due to its location, great emphasis is placed here on the quality of student education. The mission of the Koszalin University of Technology is to educate, taking into account international standards and experiences, while developing scientific research resulting from the needs of the regional and national socio-economic environment and the challenges of the modern world, as well as strengthening activities for the benefit of the environment, while maintaining special care for the natural environment. The Koszalin University of Technology can award academic degrees: habilitated doctor and doctor in 6 disciplines. It educates students in first- and second-cycle studies, both full-time and part-time. It offers 35 fields of study. The university consists of a total of eight units. Among them are six faculties, one branch and a doctoral school. The units provide education and scientific research in the following disciplines: mechanical engineering, environmental engineering, mining and energy, automation, electronics, electrical engineering and space technologies, and others. Koszalin University of Technology implements numerous international cooperation programs in science and education. The university is a developmental unit that is friendly and open to contact with the social and economic environment. It implements the goals set in its strategy, contributing to the region's development.

Actions

The potential of the Koszalin University of Technology and the number of students make the academic community a very important part of the local society. The importance of the academic community in Koszalin covers a broad spectrum of influence. It proves the city's recognition, building its prestige and the impact on the quality of human capital, especially in terms of personal development and professional qualifications." In connection with this, the Koszalin University of Technology is introducing further procedures to stimulate the working conditions of the entire academic community, including the highest standards in recruiting, assessing and promoting employees following the applicable rules. The Development Strategy of the Koszalin University of Technology until 2030 was created as a response to the challenges of the socio-economic development of Poland, with particular emphasis on the West Pomerania region, in light of global changes in Europe and the world. It takes

into account the directions of development of the European Union, Poland, the West Pomeranian Voivodeship and the city of Koszalin, which were specified in the adopted strategic documents, including:

- ✓ European Strategy for Universities, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on a European Strategy for Universities,
- ✓ University without walls. A vision for 2030, February 2021,
- ✓ Strategy for Responsible Development (perspective to 2030),
- ✓ Development Strategy for the West Pomeranian Voivodeship to 2030,
- ✓ Koszalin Development Strategy #Koszalin2030.

In defining the Development Strategy of the Koszalin University of Technology until 2030, the latest and forecasted trends in the development of science and its applications, new fields of knowledge and future technologies were taken into account, as well as forecasts regarding the global computerization of economic, technical, organizational, social and creative processes, the use of artificial intelligence, challenges related to the acquisition and use of energy, environmental protection, harmonious social development and various forms of creativity in the field of culture and art. The Development Strategy of the Koszalin University of Technology until 2030 is also focused on releasing the creative potential of employees through good organization of joint achievement of goals, supporting scientific initiatives and employee development, leading to high assessments of the entire academic environment of the University. An essential element of the strategy is optimizing the effects of joint work, adapting to changing conditions, and directing projects to create the basis for achieving long-term success for employees and students in their professional activities.

To improve the quality of scientific and teaching activities conducted within each leading discipline, Scientific Discipline Councils have been established. These councils consist of research staff selected according to the criteria specified by the Rector's order, with particular emphasis on scientific achievements in the discipline during the previous evaluation period.

Achievements

Currently, the Koszalin University of Technology is carrying out a number of tasks aimed at conducting a reliable assessment of the professional development of research workers. As part of the periodic evaluation of employees every two years, not only

publication activity is assessed, but participation in projects, patents, and services for industry, as well as organizational and teaching activity, is also assessed. After each evaluation period, the effectiveness of the applied procedures is verified and then, based on conclusions, the procedures are improved/corrected. The periodic evaluation of employees is based on data collected in the institutional repository of Knowledge Constellation of the Koszalin University of Technology, where each employee has an individual researcher profile. To streamline the subsequent periodic evaluation scheduled for 2025, it is planned to use the Electronic Document Circulation. A tool stimulating the work of scientists is the use of a qualitative supplement for contribution to the scientific achievements of the University:

https://bip.ires.pl/gfx/tu-koszalin/files/AktyPrawne-ZR/2021/nowe/Zarzadzenie_Nr_38_2020_tekst_jednolity.pdf

Another action taken as part of the strategy to strengthen the career assessment system for University employees is the decision to develop faculty strategies that are consistent with the strategy of the Koszalin University of Technology.

The key objectives of the strategy include:

Main strategic goal I: Education for the future

- I.1. Changing the organization of education
- I.2. Developing the didactic offer and building a culture of quality education
- I.3. Implementing interdisciplinarity in education
- I.4. Development of the didactic base

Main strategic goal II: Research for development

- II.1. Research quality – designing the future
- II.2. Scientific position of the University
- II.3. Scientific research and implementation for the needs of the socio-economic environment
- II.4. University for Economic Development

Main strategic objective III: Increasing potential through internationalization

The increase in internationalization will lead to the achievement of another strategic goal of the Koszalin University of Technology, namely scientific excellence. The involvement of scientists from foreign centers in research conducted at our University, including applying for external funds from the National Science Center (NCN), the National Agency for Academic Exchange (NAWA) and the National Center for Research and Development (NCBiR), will allow us to expand the spectrum of implemented

projects and strengthen their recognition in the international arena. As a result, research results at the Koszalin University of Technology will appear in the global scientific discourse. An essential element influencing the quality of scientific activity of the University's employees is the creation of activities in the area of open access policy. For this purpose, the Plan for implementing the Open Access Policy to publications and research data (hereinafter referred to as POD) has been developed. The Plan envisages the following activities with the involvement of individual units at the University:

I. Establishment of an open access team consisting of:

- ✓ Science Department
- ✓ Library
- ✓ Koszalin University of Technology Publishing House
- ✓ Research Projects Office
- ✓ Legal Advisers' Office
- ✓ Selection of the University Coordinator
- ✓ Preparation by the team of legal acts necessary to implement the plan's assumptions.

I. Within the scope of available IT tools and software, the implementation of the following procedures:

- ✓ Regulations of the Knowledge Constellation of the Koszalin University of Technology
- ✓ Regulations for collecting data in an open repository of research data
- ✓ Instructions for entering data
- ✓ Instructions for transmitting data
- ✓ Deadlines for transmitting data
- ✓ Preparation by the team of legal acts necessary for the implementation of procedures using tools and software

II. Scope of publications and research data availability:

- ✓ Publications of the Koszalin University of Technology Publishing House under temporary embargo
- ✓ Dissertations of the Koszalin University of Technology Doctoral School
- ✓ Research data based on the data management plan
- ✓ Publications that result from a research project under agreements with research funding institutions.

Action goals

The reform aimed at increasing the quality of research and assessing the development of academic careers requires adopting a number of activities carried out at two levels.

<p>2025 – 2028</p> <p>Individual Carrer Assessment</p>	<p>Development of a reliable and fair system of quantitative and qualitative assessment of research, research and teaching staff and teaching staff based on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ the diversity of employee development paths; ✓ conducting a periodic assessment of University employees in 2025; ✓ community interview based on surveys addressed to research staff of University units; ✓ establishing opinion-forming expert groups consisting of representatives of University authorities and research staff; ✓ introducing corrections based on feedback from the community interview and conclusions of expert groups; ✓ designing departments/units responsible for implementing the document "Action Plan 2025 - 2028" ✓ implementing regulations.
<p>2025 – 2028</p> <p>Open Access Policy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ development of an Institutional Open Access Policy for publications and research data (publication of Polish and English versions on the website); ✓ monitoring the POD implementation process; ✓ evaluation of the Policy (survey, metrics, statistics); ✓ promotion – increasing awareness of OA (training, information materials, tabs on the website).

Tools and resources

1. Knowledge Constellation of the Koszalin University of Technology;
2. Open Research Data Repository RepOD (Koszalin University of Technology collection);
3. Electronic Document Circulation (EOD);
4. Educational activities: training, information campaigns, a tab on the BG website (Open Science);
5. Working group for open access to publications and research data.